

Hybrid Provision of Energy based on Reliability and Resiliency by Integration of Dc Equipment

Work Package WP3

Hybrid grid enabling solutions (automation, technologies, components and validation)

Deliverable D3.9

Microgrid MV DC CB

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List of Abbreviations

ACI	Active Current Injection
AFE	Active Front End
DAB	Dual Active Bridge
DC	Direct Current
DCCB	Direct Current Circuit Breaker
HVDC	High Voltage Direct Current
MVDC	Medium Voltage Direct Current
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
RCS	Residual Current Switch
TIV	Transient Interruption Voltage
UPS	Uninterruptible Power Source
VARC	VSC-Assisted Resonant Current
VI	Vacuum Interrupter
VSC	Voltage Source Converter
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Deliverable D3.9 of the HYPERRIDE project is a demonstrator that entails the design, building and testing of two Medium Voltage Direct Current (MVDC) circuit breakers. This report presents the work done to achieve the goals of the deliverable.

The MVDC breakers will be deployed to the RWTH Aachen demonstrator grid in Germany. Work is continually done in this grid and efforts are recorded as part of Work Package (WP) 7 of HYPERRIDE.

The MVDC breaker design is based on the research and development achievements of HYPERRIDE project partner Scibreak AB. At the core of the design is the VSC-Assisted Resonant Current (VARC) concept, that is a tried and tested method for developing circuit breakers for MVDC and High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) applications (Belda, 2020). The design of the breakers in the HYPERRIDE project accounted for the relevant parameters of the Aachen demonstrator site, such as expected short circuit current amplitude, system voltage and the energy to be absorbed associated with short circuit currents.

The designed circuit breakers have been built and tested in the laboratory of Scibreak. The performed tests validate that currents with relevant magnitude such as the largest short circuit current and the largest load current during normal operation that may occur in the Aachen demonstrator can indeed be interrupted.

Moreover, the aspects of the system integration of the circuit breakers have been taken into consideration. This resulted in a set of additional equipment and software that will be necessary during the operation of the breakers in the Aachen demonstrator.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

The purpose of Task 3.9 is the construction and deployment of two MVDC circuit breakers. The circuit breakers will be installed in the RWTH Aachen demonstrator as part of the HYPERRIDE project.

The deliverable of Task 3.9 is a demonstrator according to the Grant Agreement. Therefore, this report briefly presents the targeted grid, some design steps of the circuit breakers as well as results of laboratory tests before breaker deployment to the German demonstrator.

A few deliverables (D3.1, D3.5, D3.7) of WP 3 of the project that describe aspects of the FEN Research Grid relevant for the circuit breaker design have been published by the time of the writing of this report. For the sake of better readability of this report, parts of the mentioned, already published reports are included here.

1.2 Structure of the Document

The structure of this report is outlined in followings.

Section 2 gives an overview of the part of the target grid that is relevant for this deliverable. Section 3 describes some of the circuit breaker design steps. Section 4 reports the laboratory test results and Section 5 concludes the report and outlines the activities to be undertaken in the months following the submission of this document.

2 The German Pilot

2.1 Overview

A short description of the relevant part of the RWTH Aachen demonstrator grid is given here to provide the context. This research grid (located in Aachen) is under construction and is a subject of continuous development efforts as of the writing of this report (2023), so the circuit breakers to be developed in this WP need to be designed according to the parts of the grid that already exist. The German pilot grid is aimed to become a multiterminal MVDC grid (Stieneker, Butz, Rabiee, Stagge, & Doncker, 2015).

At the time of the writing of this report, the schematic diagram of the network looks like the one shown in Figure 1. Note that the converter connected to the MVDC part of the grid on the right hand side has not been built yet.

Figure 1: Circuit schematic of the FEN MVDC Research Grid.

The Direct Current Circuit Breakers (DCCBs) will be installed on the 5 kV side of the grid. This grid is arranged in a ± 2.5 kV symmetric monopole configuration with the midpoint of the converters grounded via high impedance. Later on, after the expansion of the grid, the already existing mid-point conductor might be connected to enable bipole operation.

As displayed in Figure 1, the Active Front End (AFE) converter feeding the 5 kV part of grid has a rated power of 5 MW. This means that the largest steady-state currents in the Direct Current (DC) part of the grid will be 1 kA.

The MVDC grid part is currently consisting of the power electronics converters, cables, disconnectors and fuses.

2.2 The GE Test Bench

The GE test bench is part of the 5 kV DC part of the demonstrator grid as it is comprised of the AFE and the three-phase IGBT Dual Active Bridge (DAB) converter shown in Figure 1. As detailed in Section 6 of (Norrge et al., 2022), the joint capacitor bank of the AFE and the DAB converters is quite large and this impacts the circuit breaker design.

When the capacitors are charged to the nominal voltage of the system, a short-circuit occurring electrically close to the converters would discharge them very rapidly. The rapid discharging happens in the form of a fault current that, without countermeasures, rises quickly and reaches destructively high values. To limit the maximum rate of rise of the current, line reactors will be installed between the circuit breakers and the converters. The line reactors are dimensioned to enable the fault to be detected and interrupted by the DCCBs before the amplitude of the fault current exceeds the maximum interruptible current of the DCCBs.

3 Breaker Design

3.1 Overview

Depending on the DC system design, DCCBs or other means are used to interrupt fault currents. An alternative to DCCBs are power electronic converters that can perform fault current limitation and interruption.

For a successful current interruption in a DC line, the DC circuit breaker needs to insert a counter-voltage that forces the line current through the breaker down to zero against the voltage of the converter that powers the system. Moreover, the breaker should be able to dissipate the energy that is associated with the line current before it is interrupted as well as the energy that is supplied by the system during current suppression.

Figure 2 from (CIGRE TB 683, 2017) can be used as a reference for the definition of current interruption and suppression.

Figure 2: Definitions according to CIGRE working group A3/B4.34 TB 683.

At low- and medium voltage levels, circuit breakers creating electric arcs and using the arc voltage as the counter-voltage source are feasible. The energy associated with the line current before interruption is usually dissipated in the arc chute of such a circuit breaker.

MVDC circuit breakers based on the arc chute technology are used in certain electric traction applications and they are available on the market. However, this breaker type has its disadvantages.

tages.

One is that it is too slow to be used in future meshed MVDC grids, with a fault neutralization time of 8–10 ms for high currents and up to a few tens of milliseconds at low current levels. Another disadvantage is that the arc chute requires maintenance depending on how often current interruption is performed by the breaker and how large the interrupted currents are; in case of regular interruption of large currents, regular and costly maintenance of the breaker is necessary.

At higher voltage levels, the arc chute-based technology becomes infeasible and different technologies are used instead. One common trait of DCCB technologies at higher voltages is that surge arresters are used to dissipate the energy associated with the interruption and to clamp the voltage across the DCCB. The commutation of the fault current into the surge arrester can be accomplished in various ways, with either mechanical or semiconductor switching devices.

The VARC technology belongs to one of the four types of DCCB technologies detailed in (CIGRE TB 683, 2017). It may further be considered to be a subtype of the Active Current Injection (ACI) technology.

At the base of its operating principle is the idea of creating an artificial current zero-crossing in a Vacuum Interrupter (VI). This is achieved by the use of a Voltage Source Converter (VSC) and a properly dimensioned resonant circuit connected in parallel to the VI. When switched correctly, the VSC excites a resonant current flowing through the resonant circuit and the VI that increases in magnitude in each switching cycle. Once the resonant current is sufficiently large, it cancels out the current flowing through the VI of the circuit breaker, thus creating a current zero and allowing the VI to interrupt. The current through the breaker is then instead forced to flow through the only remaining parallel path - a surge arrester. The voltage drop across the surge arrester is large enough to suppress the fault current to zero. At that point, a mechanical switch can interrupt any small remaining currents.

The circuit diagram of a VARC circuit breaker along with typical waveforms during a breaking operation are illustrated in Figure 3. The circuit diagram is divided into three branches according to the functions that they perform. The green branch is the main branch, which conducts the current under normal conditions. The current then flows through the metallic contacts of a vacuum interrupter.

When the circuit breaker is in its closed position, the line current flows through the mechanical contacts of the VI. At the moment current interruption by the circuit breaker is ordered ("trip order" in Figure 3), a fast actuator starts to open and thus, separates the VI contacts. Less than 1.5 ms is sufficient for the VI contact separation to be large enough to withstand the Transient Interruption Voltage (TIV) that appears across the VI once its current is forced to zero. The VSC is used together with the resonant circuit to excite a resonant current (i_{VSC} in Figure 3) that creates this artificial current zero in the VI.

Once the current is zero in the VI, first it has been commutated into the resonant capacitor in the branch of the VSC of the breaker as displayed in Figure 3. The capacitor is charged very quickly to the knee voltage of the surge arrester, after which the surge arrester starts conducting. By the time the current has commutated from the resonant capacitor to the surge arrester, the voltage across the surge arrester reached its discharge voltage level. The line current conduction occurs together with the insertion of the counter-voltage, therefore the line current is suppressed over time (refer to Figure 2).

Let I_{BR} denote the amplitude of the largest currents that may be interrupted by the DCCBs. In

Figure 3: VARC breaker main circuit and typical waveforms during a breaking operation.

this case, I_{BR} is 8 kA.

3.2 Resonant circuit

The resonant circuit is made up of an inductor and a capacitor bank. Let L denote the inductance of the resonant inductor and the stray inductance of the leads connecting the components of the resonant circuit. Let also C denote the capacitance of the capacitor bank.

With L and C , the characteristic impedance of the resonant circuit, Z_{LC} can be expressed as

$$Z_{LC} = \sqrt{\frac{L}{C}} \quad (1)$$

The resonant frequency of the resonant circuit, f_{LC} is

$$f_{LC} = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{LC}} \quad (2)$$

Depending on what the targeted Z_{LC} and f_{LC} are, the ratio of the stray inductance of the leads to L is in the range of several percents. This means that the impact of the stray inductances should be taken into consideration when designing the resonant circuit.

As detailed in (Ängquist et al., 2019), the characteristic impedance of the circuit breaker should be adapted to the clamping voltage of the surge arresters in order to limit the current that can flow through the resonant circuit and the VSC of the breaker.

Accounting for the clamping voltage of the surge arresters installed in the Aachen demonstrator as well as how much margin they permit when selecting the clamping voltage of the breaker surge arresters, it is concluded that Z_{LC} should be less than 1Ω , preferably it should be in the $0.7 \Omega - 0.9 \Omega$ range.

From previous experience and laboratory measurements, it is estimated that an f_{LC} in the range of 8–14 kHz would ensure reliable breaker operation.

Combining 1 with 2 and substituting 0.75Ω into Z_{LC} and 10.6 kHz into f_{LC} , the inductance of the resonant circuit is retrieved as

$$L = \frac{Z_{LC}}{2\pi f_{LC}} = 11.2 \mu\text{H} \quad (3)$$

and the resonant capacitor size is retrieved as

$$C = \frac{1}{2\pi f_{LC} Z_{LC}} = 20 \mu\text{F} \quad (4)$$

It is estimated that the leads of the circuit result in added stray inductances totalling in the $1\text{--}1.5 \mu\text{H}$ range. Therefore the resonant inductor should have an inductance of roughly $10 \mu\text{H}$ (which is the difference of the total resonant circuit inductance L and the stray inductances).

3.3 VSC

The VSC comprises power electronic switches and the DC-link capacitor bank. These capacitors store the energy needed to develop the resonant current during line current interruption.

The VSC of the circuit breakers to be built as part of HYPERRIDE is a half-bridge converter. There is no big difference for the operation of the VARC circuit breaker if the VSC is a half-bridge or a full-bridge. If the resonant circuit is the same and the resonant current should be the same for both cases, then the difference between using a half- or full-bridge converter is just the voltage level of the VSC. A half-bridge VSC needs to be designed for double the voltage of a corresponding full-bridge VSC to excite the resonant current at the same speed. The half-bridge then needs higher-voltage-rated capacitors and semiconductors, but it has only one VSC leg, which saves some cost and complexity. The choice of using either the half- or the full-bridge converter variant is dependent on the practicality of the design as well as on component cost considerations.

The VSC of the circuit breaker excites the resonant circuit to produce the current that counters the line current flowing through the VI. Let U_{DC} denote the voltage of the DC-link of the converter. When the VSC is first switched on, a current ΔI starts flowing in the resonant circuit. The amplitude of the undamped sinusoidal current excited by this first voltage step is

$$\Delta I = \frac{U_{DC}}{Z_{LC}} \quad (5)$$

At the next VSC commutation, the resonant circuit is subjected to a negative voltage step relative to the voltage preceding the switching instant. This negative voltage step also causes a resonant current with amplitude ΔI to flow. If this second voltage step is applied when the current due the first switch-on changes polarity, then the current excited by the negative voltage step adds to this, resulting in a current with an amplitude of $2\Delta I$ to flow.

If the VSC is repeatedly switched at resonant current zeros, the undamped sinusoidal resonant current increases by ΔI every half period (refer to the yellow waveforms of Figure 3). Note that the consecutive current steps are slightly decreasing because U_{DC} is dropping as the DC-link energy is gradually used up for the resonant current development.

The design regarding the capacitance of the capacitors and the maximum DC-link voltage needs to take into consideration relevant semiconductor switch ratings, ohmic losses of the resonant circuit as well as certain requirements for the circuit breaker in question such as how many 'interrupt' operations need to be performed in quick succession. The latter means the number of operations that need to be performed with so short time in between them that the charging circuit of the DC-link cannot fully replenish the lost energy meanwhile.

3.4 Mechanical design

The mechanical design resulted in a compact breaker setup. The design also makes sure that the breaker components have sufficient clearance and creepage distances from other components when the difference of their electric potentials requires this.

Figure 4 shows the assembled circuit breaker during the laboratory tests.

Figure 4: MVDC breaker in the laboratory.

The dimensions of the breaker are approximately 1.27 m x 0.82 m x 0.56 m.

The mechanical design of the circuit breakers should also take into account that the breakers will be part of a larger system. Integration into the RWTH Aachen demonstrator requires that the breakers have their own enclosures. The purpose of the enclosure is to protect the grid operator from the impact of a breaker surge arrester explosion and to prevent unauthorised

access to the breaker. Moreover, the enclosure also houses the auxiliary power system, the interface Printed Circuit Board (PCB) and the Residual Current Switch (RCS) (detailed in the next subsection).

Figure 5: Circuit breaker and residual current switch inside the enclosure.

Figure 5 depicts a rendered image of how the circuit breaker and the RCS would look like inside the enclosure. Figure 6 displays the breaker enclosure when its door is closed as well as the positioning of the interface PCB.

The dimensions of the enclosure are approximately 2 m x 1 m x 0.8 m.

Integration of the breakers into their enclosures was not necessary for the laboratory tests, but the breakers will be shipped from Scibreak in their cabinets.

3.5 Auxiliary equipment

The integration of the DCCBs into the Aachen demonstrator grid requires additional devices to be installed together with the circuit breakers. The following paragraphs describe the most

Figure 6: Circuit breaker enclosure with interface PCB.

important of these.

- Line reactors

As referenced in Subsection 2.2, rapidly rising and large currents result, if the large capacitor banks of the GE Testbench experience a short-circuit when they are charged to the nominal system voltage. In order to prevent the occurrence of severely damaging electric arcs, line reactors will be connected in series with the VARC circuit breakers.

Based on grid simulations, 500 μH of inductance connected in series with the breakers in each pole limits the rate of rise of fault currents to a level at which the VARC breakers can clear any fault.

Figure 7 shows a drawing of the reactor stack comprising two, 500 μH reactors.

- Communication interface

The circuit breakers are designed to work autonomously. This means that a breaker is

Figure 7: Design of the line reactor stack inside its enclosure.

equipped with a line current sensor and a fast control system that can trip the breaker.

The breaker control system is on significantly higher potential than the ground. If communication with the circuit breaker has to be implemented in an electrically non-isolated way, for example by using an Ethernet-cable, then an additional, digital protective relay needs to be integrated into the breaker. This interfacing digital relay is on system ground potential and it is programmed to manage the Ethernet-based or serial communication between the circuit breaker and other devices of the grid. Information is exchanged between the interfacing digital relay and the breaker control system via optical fibre.

- Auxiliary power system

The energy storing systems of the circuit breaker, i.e. the VSC and the actuator mechanism moving the VI contacts as well as the on-board control system and other electronic components require power to be fed to the appliance and to be converted to specific voltage levels.

As the power source available for this purpose in the Aachen demonstrator grid is a single-phase 230 V outlet, the conversion will take place in the auxiliary power converters integrated into the breaker. This system includes an Uninterruptible Power Source (UPS) to avoid the loss of breaker functionality should the grid power outlet lose power temporarily.

- Residual current switch

The VARC circuit breaker needs a separate mechanical switch to perform final galvanic isolation after a fault has been cleared.

It is advantageous from the grid operator point of view if the integration of the VARC breaker and the RCS is so that the VARC breaker control system can determine when the RCS should be operated and it can issue the correct orders to the switch, i.e., the operator only has to interact with the VARC breaker. This switch is also used to reclose the breaker. By reclosing with this separate switch, the fast-acting DCCBs is ready to clear a fault immediately when the contacts of the RCS close.

4 Laboratory Tests

The results of two different laboratory tests performed are presented in this section.

Some background information on the test circuit used for the laboratory tests is given first. The circuit is of a type using precharged capacitors and its equivalent resistance and its inductor size are $25\text{ m}\Omega$ and $800\text{ }\mu\text{H}$, respectively. More details about the test circuit can be found in Section 4 of (Hatsagi, Nee, Norrga, & Modeer, 2021).

1 kA tests have been performed in the laboratory to show that currents associated with load switching during normal operation of the Aachen demonstrator can be interrupted by the circuit breakers.

Figure 8: Interruption of 1 kA.

As depicted in Figure 8, interruption of 1.37 kA has been achieved in 1 ms after the circuit breaker was tripped. Even though the current was slightly larger than 1 kA, reducing the amplitude of the current only makes the interruption less demanding for the breaker.

The 8 kA tests have been performed to demonstrate that the circuit breakers are capable of interrupting currents equivalent in amplitude to the fault currents that may occur in worst-case short-circuit scenarios in the Aachen demonstrator.

As shown in Figure 9, interruption of 8.6 kA has been achieved in 1.2 ms after the circuit breaker was tripped. The test verifies that even currents that are slightly larger than 8 kA can be successfully interrupted by the MVDC circuit breakers.

Figure 9: Interruption of 8 kA.

5 Conclusions

This report has given an overview of some of the parameters of the RWTH Aachen demonstrator grid relevant for the breaker design as well as some of the design steps of the circuit breakers to be deployed as part of the HYPERRIDE projects.

By performing laboratory tests whose results are included in this report, it has been demonstrated that the MVDC circuit breakers built for the HYPERRIDE project are capable of interrupting even the worst-case short-circuit fault currents that may occur in the MVDC part of the RWTH Aachen demonstrator.

The upcoming tests to be done in the period following the submission of this report are the on-site short-circuit tests. Later on (scheduled for the first half of 2024), tests of the converters protected by the circuit breakers being run at full power are to be performed. These tests would be part of the demonstration of the whole test grid (WP 7 of HYPERRIDE).

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